

DEVELOPMENT OF FUTURE TEACHERS' SKILLS FOR CONFLICTOGENIC SITUATIONS

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Abstract. *In the process of education, as in all areas, specialists face conflict-causing situations. In this educational process, the teacher's ability to control himself in conflict situations, to eliminate conflicts, to anticipate unexpected conflicts, and to use the functions that determine the fair resolution of relations, is aimed at achieving good results. The debate about these issues was reflected in the content of the article.*

Keywords: *function, conflictology, conflict, pedagogical process, interests, conflict resolution, compromise.*

Today, the range of approaches related to the development of the ability to resolve conflicts, the development of effective behavioral skills, and the teaching of behavioral strategies in a conflict situation is expanding. Undoubtedly, the conflictological problem is becoming the leading scientific and research work of pedagogues.

As part of the socio-psychological approach, training programs have been developed to teach conflict resolution skills, there are many recommendations for preventing or ending conflicts (mainly in management positions). Modern developments are aimed at regulation and management of conflicts. Although these works are based on the understanding of the positive functions of conflict, their content is constructed as the elimination of negative experiences and the acquisition of "winning" skills in conflict interactions.

The teacher's conflictological training is characterized by the acquisition and use of special, professionally oriented conflictological knowledge, which is necessary for the perception of professional conflicts and the subsequent implementation of professional functions in a professional conflict. At the same time, the teacher's professional conflictological preparation is characterized not only by the skills of preventing and solving conflicts in the educational environment, but also by the formation of conflictological competence among students.

Conflictological preparation, in the final analysis, is interpreted by N.E. Serebrovskaya as follows:

the state of the organization (special professional culture is diagnosed; information culture is enriched);

helps to understand the participants of the conflict and the problem in the conflict more deeply (objects of special professional, psychological, informational and methodological culture are indicated);

weakens mental stress (supporting the functions of psychological culture);

creates intellectual and emotional tension accompanied by a clash of different strategies for solving problems (there is an activation of methodical culture);

prevents destructive confrontation of conflict participants and unites members of the work team (supporting the functions of communicative culture).

Formation of conflictological literacy and conflictological competence forms the basis of teacher's conflictological training. Accordingly, conflictual literacy is the main level of conflictual preparation, manifested in everyday intuitive and verbal experience, in the mythological mind of a person, which allows constructive resolution of problems and contradictions without a good understanding of the mechanisms underlying them.

The typology of school conflicts is diverse and is represented by the following types of conflict: between children; child, children - teacher; children - administration; between teachers; teacher - parents; teacher - administration; between parents; parents - administration.

The following can be distinguished as the main causes of conflicts in secondary schools:

- struggle for leadership (between children, teachers, parents);
- discrimination of children, parents, teachers by the administration, etc.;
- school success of children and adults; financial capabilities of schoolchildren and teachers;
- assessing children's progress;
- pedagogical experience, the role of the teacher in the teaching staff, the importance of taught subjects;
- forms of strict regulation and control of school life; structural and functional problems of the educational institution;
- improper management style; violation of moral standards, etc.

Researchers (L.M. Mitina, M.M. Ribakov) refer to the acute situations of pedagogical activity:

- cases of interaction between the teacher and students in the classroom (violation of discipline and behavior rules, unexpected conflict situations, disobedience, ignoring the teacher's requirements, "stupid" questions, etc.);

- situations that arise in relations with colleagues and school administration (sharp differences of opinion, overloading of assignments, conflicts in the distribution of the academic load, excessive control of academic work, ill-conceived news at school, etc.);

- situations of interaction between the teacher and the parents of the students (differences in the assessment of the student by the teacher and parents, parents' inattention to the process of raising children, etc.).

The negative effects of stressful factors cause double stress to the teacher: informational stress (information overload, the need to make quick decisions with a high degree of responsibility for the consequences) and emotional stress (the appearance of emotional stress, changes in the nature of activities, behavioral disorders).

The concepts of "conflictological culture of a person" and "conflictological culture of an expert" should be distinguished.

The conflictological culture of a person consists of a person's desire (need, desire) and ability to prevent and resolve social conflicts: interpersonal and inter-national. In modern society, the resolution of social conflict is the most important factor of socialization of the individual.

The specialist's conflictological culture is characterized by the acquisition and use of special, professionally oriented conflictological knowledge, which is necessary for the perception of professional conflicts and the subsequent implementation of professional functions in the conditions of professional conflict.

Formation of conflictological culture is determined by experts in different ways, thus, M.M. According to Rybakova, conflictological culture is the highest level of human conflictological training. Conflict preparation consists of the following components:

conflict literacy - as a basic level that is manifested not in knowledge of the mechanisms and technologies of conflict analysis and working with them, but in their intuitive understanding, which allows a person to solve conflicts constructively in general;

conflictological competence - as a special level of conflictological training, it consists in obtaining a system of scientific and practical knowledge about the conflict, specially formed and developed during the specialist's studies [4].

Accordingly, conflictological culture is the highest level of conflictological training of a person. It consists of various components ("cultures") connected to a single complex and closely related to each other.

The elements of this complex include: culture of thinking, culture of feelings, communicative culture, culture of value-semantic field, behavioral conflictological culture.

Therefore:

the culture of thinking is based on theoretical ideas about conflict and consists of a person's ability to rationally analyze the conflict, distinguish the main and secondary things, and use the conclusions obtained in his actions;

the culture of emotions - these are skills related to working with emotions, first of all your own: understanding emotions, ability to work with negative emotions, showing empathy, etc.;

communicative culture - readiness to conduct dialogue, partnership conversation;

behavioral conflict culture - the ability to work directly with the conflict, that is, to resolve the conflict, to prevent its escalation, to manage the conflict.

Based on the above definitions, we can distinguish the concept of conflictological culture.

Conflictological culture is a product of a person's social life and social activity, which becomes a certain type and system of general culture and is manifested in the person's readiness and ability to describe, learn and work. In this work, we understand culture from the perspective of an axiological approach.

The model of conflictological culture of a person should consist of certain blocks, which together form the structure of conflictological culture and are determined by specific functions:

The theoretical-information block consists of theoretical ideas about the conflict. This includes knowledge about what conflict is, its constructive and destructive functions, structure, conflict dynamics, etc.

So we can conclude:

conflict means a type of social interaction characterized by a conscious differentiation of interests, beliefs, values, etc.;

in this study, the expert's conflictological culture is understood as a qualitative description of the expert's professional life in a professional environment prone to conflicts;

Despite the different understanding of cultural culture by experts, the recognition of conflict as an inevitable, everyday and frequent phenomenon makes the specific norms and rules of behavior in conflict situations relevant, the problem of developing a person's conflictological consciousness, the ability to predict, prevent, resolve conflicts. constitutes a single approach in the concept of "conflictological culture of an individual".

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